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Research Article

**THE STUDY OF THE INFECTIONS OF THE SURGICAL SITE
AND ASSOCIATED VARIABLES IN PATIENTS HAVING
GENERAL SURGERIES**¹Sana Mushtaq, ²Ayesha Zujaja, ³Aamna Qayyum¹Nishtar Medical University, Multan., ²Nishtar Medical University, Multan., ³Nishtar Medical University, Multan.**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Objective: To assess factors that contribute to the development of surgical site infections in patients undergoing general surgery.

Place and Duration: This research was carried out from may 2019 to april 2020 in the Surgery Department of the Nishtar Hospital in Multan.

Materials and Methods: The study included patients with surgical site infections developed after general operations. Information was noted such as obesity, surgical time, hospital length, high blood pressure, diabetes mellitus, smoking and blood transfusions.

Results: The study included 80 patients over 18 years of age. Around 52 per cent of patients were 45 to 60 years of age, while 15 per cent were over 60 years of age. The remaining cases ranged from 18 to 30 and from 31 to 45 years of age. The study consisted of 57 (71.25%) men and 33 (41.25%) women. Smoking (20.1 per cent), multiple blood transfusions (14.2 per cent), obesity (14.2 per cent) and lengthy hospitalization were the causes of surgical site infection (16.2 per cent). Hypertension occurred in 11.1% of patients and diabetes in 12.4% of patients. Additional 11.8% were unknown causes.

Conclusion: Factors related to site infection development included multiple blood transfusions, prolonged hospital stays, smoking, obesity and emergency surgery.

Key Words: SSI, Surgical site infection, General Surgery

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INTRODUCTION:

The surgical site can be infected in surgical areas after surgery. Surgical site infection (SSI) can typically be prevented and accidental. It has been linked to increased health care morbidity and costliness (Bibi et al., 2011). The occurrence of SSI varies among hospitals worldwide. The SSI rate in literature is reported to be 2.5% to 41.90%. According to an estimated SSI, approximately 1,400,000 cases occur in 2 per cent of surgeries. The severity of SSI may vary according to the case (Alfonso-Sanchez et al. 2017). The most common complication is considered as well as nosocomial infection. It comprises 20% of healthcare-related infections and 38% of nosocomial infections after surgery.

Previous research has shown that 13% of surgical patients developed SSIs in Pakistan (Jenks et al. 2014). Different research projects were carried out to develop SSIs and understand different risk factors contributing to their occurrence. Research has also been carried out to determine how these factors can be controlled clinically (Taylor, Gosman & Kelley 2017). Consequently, various research works have shown different SSI risk factors. Some studies have shown that transfusion is a significant risk factor for SSI development (Shah, Singh & Rathod 2017). Other factors indicated by previous studies include increased age, diabetes mellitus, pre-operative hospital residence, ASA score greater than 3, emergency operation, contaminated operating sites and prolonged surgical procedure duration. However, a recent systemic review has shown that Pakistan lacks data on postoperative injury infections (Tariq et al. 2017). It is essential to determine its prevalence and responsible factors with a massive SSI increase over the past few years. The World Health Organization (WHO) has nevertheless argued that most underdeveloped countries do not have adequate SSI data. In order to implement SSI prevention measures, its risk factors must be identified (Michael 2017). This study is therefore intended to identify responsible factors for SSI in people undergoing general operations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This research was carried out from may 2019 to april 2020 in the Surgery Department of the Nishtar Hospital in Multan. This cross-sectional study involved patients who developed after general surgeries with surgical site infections. Patients over 18 years of age, who were both sexes, were included. Patients were omitted who were not willing to participate in the study. Patients with malignancy and tuberculosis diagnosis were also excluded. Wound infection was classified based on surgical site

infection. Information such as diabetes mellitus, obesity, prolonged surgical time, hospitalization, smoking, blood transfusions and high blood pressure have been noted. The data collected were analyzed by SPSS v.17.

RESULTS:

Eighty cases of surgical site infection were included in the study. About 52 per cent of patients ranged between 45 and 60 years, compared to 15 per cent over 60 years. The remaining cases were between 18-30 and 31-45 years of age. The study consisted of 57 (71.25%) men and 33 (41.25%) women. Smoking (20.1%), multiple blood transfusions (14.2%), obesity (14.2%) and prolonged hospitalization were the leading causes of operational site infections (16.2 per cent). Hypertension occurred in 11.1% of patients and diabetes in 12.4% of patients. Additional 11.8% were unknown causes.

DISCUSSION:

The majority of patients in this study were over 45 years of age. Age is an independent risk factor for SSI development, according to Neumayer et al. (2007). The same was found in this study, where the risk of developing SSI was significantly increased for patients over 45 years. Many (71%) cases of emergency surgery related to SSI development. The results were similar to those found by Sanabria et al. (2014). The development of SSI in 14.2% of patients was due to obesity. Obesity is a significant risk factor for SSI through research by Rasul et al. (2016). The reason can be poor adipose tissue vascularization, which leads to tissue oxygenation, which leads to an increased risk of SSI. Obese patients may, therefore have longer and more complex operations. Smokers have reduced progress in treating wounds, which is caused by reduced oxygen transport and vasoconstrictive blood effects. 20.1% of patients in this study developed SSI due to smoking. In a study by Graante et al. (2008), smokers developed SSI significantly compared to non-smokers. Smokers who smoked more cigarettes, therefore had additional opportunities to SSI. Much previous research has shown that hyperglycemia is positively associated with perioperative complications. The SSI was developed in 12.4% of diabetic patients in this study. Ata et al. (2010) stressed that postoperative hyperglycemia is a significant cause of SSI. In the same vein, Bibi et al. (2011) claimed that the risk of developing SSI in diabetic patients is 3.6 times higher than in non-diabetic ones. 14.2% of patients in this study developed SSI due to multiple blood transfusions. However, the Micheal et al. (2017) study claimed that blood transfusion was associated with SSI

development. It may be connected to organ space and SSI septic shock, created after resection of the colon. While transfusion is a lifesaving procedure, it is associated with many complications, including infection. 16.2% of persons with prolonged hospital stay developed SSI in this study. Malik et al.'s (2015) work showed that people with SSIs have a high difference from non-SSIs in their hospital stay. The main reason for the increase in affiliate costs is a prolonged hospital stay due to SSI. Florio et al.'s work (2006) has also shown that obesity, extended preoperation, AIDS and diabetes contribute to SSI.

CONCLUSION:

The risk factors positively related to surgical site infection development included extended hospitalization, smoking, obesity, an emergency operation, and multiple blood transfusions. Surgeons should be aware of infection development in patients with these respective factors.

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